

Original Article

TRAVEL MOTIVATIONS AND THEIR IMPACT ON VISITOR EXPERIENCE AT PORT HARCOURT PLEASURE PARK

Chukwuemeka Ugochukwu Nwosu and Nneka Ifeyinwa Ibe

Department of Hospitality Management & Tourism, Faculty of Management Sciences, University of Port Harcourt, Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13918276>

This study investigates the relationship between travel motivation and tourist satisfaction at Port Harcourt Pleasure Park. It adopted a cross-sectional survey as a research design. The total population consists of one hundred (100) tourists surveyed using convenient sampling technique. Face validity was employed. Cronbach Alpha was used to ascertain the reliability of instrument. Kendall's Coefficient of Concordance (τ_b) was used to analyse the hypotheses while percentage was used to analyse tourists' demographic characteristics with the aid of statistical package for social sciences (20.0). This study found that travel motivation has a positive significant relationship with tourist satisfaction in Port Harcourt Pleasure Park. This study concludes that travel motivation that is measured on perceived attractiveness and relaxation has the capacity of fulfilling tourist satisfactions in destinations.

Keywords: Travel motivation, tourist satisfaction, perceived attractiveness, relaxation, destination image, responsiveness.

Introduction

Travel motivation is triggered by tourist behavioural antecedents which correlate with the outcome or expectation from the visit. Thus, the movement of tourists from one destination to another are motivated by several factors such as relaxation, events, pilgrimages, conferences, escape from disaster prone zones, pleasure, business, family reunion and engagements, knowledge acquisition, security, discovery of new relationship to mentioned but a few. This movement wouldn't be possible if tourism environment is not properly prepared for visitors' comfort and serenity. However, tourism thrives in an environment where there is political stability, adequate security, functional infrastructure as well as continuity of policies that promotes tourism activities. It is based on this premise that visitors feel satisfy to revisit and to recommend same to families, colleagues, friends and neighbours. Tourist satisfaction is significant to tourism development and promotion (Ninemeier and Perdue, 2008). Chang (2007) added that tourists wellbeing is an offshoot of how well they were treated the first time they visited tourist sites. March and Woodside (2005) maintained that destination loyalty is as a result of the satisfaction derived from a visit to tourism community. Thus, tourist satisfaction has the capacity of attracting more people from other countries through recommendations and electronic discovery. When tourists are satisfy with the services they received including destination behaviour, they will plan another visit to the same tourism venue but when they don't receive good treatment, they will neither recommend nor return back another time.

Original Article

In line with the above, Solnet (2011) asserts that tourists who are satisfied with a destination are likely to become loyal and visit repeatedly; will deepen their relationships with the destination and its individual service providers; are more likely to recommend the destination to others; and demonstrate less price sensitivity.

Nevertheless, previous researchers have empirically investigated tourist satisfaction in the various hospitality industry (Hsi-Ying, 2016; Bashar and Al-Ajlani, 2012); but their investigations have not captured Port Harcourt Pleasure Park. Thus, the point of departure in this study is to investigate the relationship between travel motivation and tourist satisfaction in Port Harcourt Pleasure Park, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of this study is to investigate the relationship between travel motivation and tourist satisfaction at Port Harcourt Pleasure Park. Specifically, it sought to;

1. ascertain the relationship between perceived attractiveness and destination image
2. examine the relationship between relaxation and responsiveness

Research Hypotheses

Based on the specific objectives, the following null hypotheses were formulated.

HO1: perceived attractiveness has no significant relationship with destination image

HO2: relaxation has no significant relationship with responsiveness

Review of Related Literature Travel motivation

Travelling from one destination to another is usually engineered, stimulated or motivated by environmental triggered factors. Thus, this section reviews motivation and travel motivation. Sinding and Waldstrom (2014) argued that motivation is the arousal, direction and maintenance of human behaviour towards attaining some goal. Mullins (2011) affirmed that motivation is the direction and persistence of individual action. Beerli and Martín (2004) perceived motivation as the need that drives an individual to act in a certain way to achieve the desired satisfaction. Hsu and Huang (2008) perceived travel motivation as the reasons why tourists travel. Compton (1979) classified travel motivation as intrinsic (push) or extrinsic (pull). Oom do Valle, Silva, Mendes and Guerreiro (2006) contended that push motivations are in line with tourist's desire and emotional frame of mind while pull motivations are the features or characteristics of the destination to be visited.

However, tourists who visit Port Harcourt Pleasure parks are motivated by facilities such as adequate security, nearness to city (location), climbing tower, virtual reality games, kids bouncy castle, wellbeing fitness machines, mini boat ride, mini golf course, mini soccer field, jogging circuit, paint ball, spacious parking lot, pedal boats, restaurant, water steps, playground especially for children, 5D and 9D cinemas to mentioned but a few (www.phpleasurepark.com). McIntosh and Geoldner (1986) cited in Hsi-Ying (2016) summed travel motivation and tourism activities into commercial, physical, interpersonal, cultural and prestige. Fodness (1994) suggested five typologies of travel as it relates to tourism as; knowledge or culture, reward maximization or pleasure and sensation, educational motives, self-esteem and ego-enhancement or social prestige, punishment maximization or escape stimulus-avoidance. Researchers have also examined travel motivation of tourists on destinations with findings. Thiumsak and Ruangkanjanases (2016) investigated factors influencing international visitors to revisit Bangkok. Their results revealed that perceived attractiveness on accommodation, shopping, restaurant & food, and attitude of Thai people, relaxation & recreation, and the overall destination image constitute travel motivating factors. Bashar and Al-Ajlani (2012) investigated the motivating factors for foreign tourists to rural site in Jordan,

Original Article

village of Petra. Their finding shows that rural environment, facilities, weather, cultural link and adventure are the factors that stimulate foreign tourists to visit.

Perceived attractiveness

Perceived attractiveness is an attribute of travel motivation especially as it concerns Port Harcourt Pleasure Park. This is the reason why Hu and Ritchie (1993) and Um, Chon and Ro (2006) accentuates that a tourist's perceived attractiveness measures how well a destination can perform to meet the crucial criteria of holiday destination. In addition, Bowie and Chang (2005) elucidated that different tourists may have different perception towards the attractiveness of a destination as their backgrounds in terms of culture, age, experience, marital status and financial status might be entirely diverse. Port Harcourt Pleasure Park is attractive, exceptional due to its beauty and serene environment. The location of the park makes it very attractive to any visitor or passerby thereby drawing their attention to visit. Tourists are attracted to visit Port Harcourt Pleasure on the basis of easy access, price affordability and security.

Relaxation

Another determinant of travel motivation is relaxation (Zhang and Lam, 1999; Bashar and Al-Ajlani, 2012). Tourists travel to destinations to relax after a long day work to ease stress. Destinations are usually the best place to discuss certain issues that need urgent attention with family members or friends. Port Harcourt Pleasure Park serves as a relaxation avenue for tourists. The choice of the park remains with the tourists who made decisions to visit and recommend same to colleagues and relatives. One of the thrilling relaxation sections in the park is the virtual cinema (9D). The 9D is virtual reality where viewers don't need to wear VR glasses before watching movies. It consists of three revolutionary new products; namely interactive cinema with 360°rotation function, Immersive Glasses and Breakthrough VR entertainment content platform (<https://phpleasurepark.com>). The restaurant is another amazing world cuisine centre where tourists are treated with African as well as Chinese dishes.

Tourist satisfaction

Distinguishing satisfaction from tourist satisfaction, Kotler and Keller (2009) opined that satisfaction is a person's feelings of pleasure or disappointment resulting from comparing a product's perceived performance (or outcome) in relation to his or her expectations. Building tourist to satisfaction, Vanacore and Etro (2002) stressed that tourist satisfaction is the overall assessment carried out by tourist about a particular product or service within a certain period. Tourist satisfaction is also a measure on how tourism services or products are supplied by tourists' practitioners in order to meet their expectation (Igi-global.com, 2019). Tourist satisfaction is a function of pre-travel expectations and post-travel experiences; which means that the tourists are satisfied when experiences go beyond their expectations (Nor, Shareena, Siti and Syahmi, 2016). It is also known as a state of been satisfied, a feeling of completeness or ones level of approval. In addition, Severt, Wong, Chen, and Breiter (2007) contended that tourist satisfaction is the extent to which tourists are fulfilled from destination experience including the service or product received during the visit as well as their expectation. Tourist derived satisfaction through the services they received; the value of the product compared with costs associated it and their previous expectations. Baker and Crompton (2000) referred to satisfaction as a tourist's emotional state after exposure to the destination. Tourists can be satisfied if there are positive confirmations of their expectations (Le, 2010; Schiffman and Kanuk, 2004). However, Vuuren, Lombard and Tonder (2012) contended that tourist satisfaction is the emotional

Original Article

response that occurs when measuring the expectations and product obtained through physical contact with the product. Tourist satisfaction refers to positive feeling that tourist display to mean their appetite during and after service is encouraging and recommendable. In this study destination image and perceived quality will be utilized as determinants of tourist satisfaction in the Port Harcourt Pleasure Park, Nigeria. However, scholars has carried out empirical studies on tourist satisfaction of various destinations and found different variables playing out as attractors. Sharma (2017) investigated tourist satisfaction on accommodation at Southern Rajasthan, India. It was found tourist satisfaction has positive significant relationship with accommodation. Nor, Shareena, Siti and Syahmi (2016) investigated antecedents of tourist satisfaction in Langkawi Island, Malaysia. Their results revealed that destination image, tourist expectations, costs and risks, and social-security have positive and significant influence on tourist satisfaction. Suanmali (2014) investigated the factors affecting tourist satisfaction in the Northern part of Thailand. Suanmali's finding revealed that cost of staying, hospitality, attractions and accessibility, infrastructure is the major factors affecting tourist satisfaction.

Destination image

Crompton (1979) in Hsi-Ying (2016) opined that image is the sum of the beliefs, impressions, viewpoints and feelings that people have about certain objects, actions or events. Hsi-Ying (2016) contended that the central thesis of destination image is that it has a crucial role on individual's travel purchase associated decision making as well as individual traveler's satisfaction/dissatisfaction. Kandampully and Hu (2007) added that destination image is significant attribute that enhances tourist loyalty. Tang (2007) argued that enterprise image is generally related with the business name, the product variety, architecture, tradition and ideology of a firm. It is the sum of beliefs, ideas and impressions that a consumer has on an organisation. Chi and Qu (2008) viewed destination image as tourist mental representation of the knowledge, feelings, and overall perception of a particular destination.

Responsiveness

Responsiveness is one of the attributes of service quality dimensions by Parasuraman, Berry and Zeithmal (1988). Responsiveness is the willingness or readiness of Port Harcourt Pleasure Park to provide services timely as well as assist visitors on arrival. Tourist satisfaction is a function of how well service attendants approached them and request how they can assist them. Tourist arrival at the Port Harcourt Pleasure Park is one of the major reasons why most tourists prefer coming back after a visit. Employees working in the park knew quite well that their monthly income is as a result of the number of tourists that visit the park and hence, they have received instructions from their supervisors on the need to be prompt while rendering services.

Research Methodology

This study adopted a cross-sectional survey as a research design. The total population consists of one hundred (100) tourists' surveyed using convenient sampling technique. One hundred copies of questionnaire were administered but seventy-eight (78) was filled correctly and used for data analysis. Face validity was employed to ascertain the validity of the instrument. Reliability of instrument falls within .70 - .80 alpha (α) values using Cronbach Alpha. Perceived attractiveness, Relaxation, Destination image and responsiveness were measured on five-point Likert scale ranging from 5= Strongly agree; 4 = Agree; 3= Disagree; 2 = Strongly disagree 1= Neither agree nor disagree. Kendall's Coefficient of Concordance

Original Article

(tau_b) was used to analyse the hypotheses while percentage was used to analyse tourists’ demographic characteristics with the aid of statistical package for social sciences (20.0).

Results Table 1: Gender of Tourists

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	52	69.3	69.3	69.3
Valid Female	23	30.7	30.7	100.0
Total	75	100.0	100.0	

Table 1 above shows the gender of tourist surveyed at Port Harcourt Pleasure Park. From the table; 52 tourists representing 69.3% were males while 23 representing 30.7% were females.

Figure 1: Bar charts showing Gender of Tourist

Table 2: Educational Background of Tourists’

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Secondary	13	17.3	17.3	17.3
Primary	6	8.0	8.0	25.3
Others	10	13.3	13.3	38.7
Valid Master	10	13.3	13.3	52.0
Bachelor	36	48.0	48.0	100.0
Total	75	100.0	100.0	

Table 2 above shows the educational background of tourists at Port Harcourt Pleasure Park. 13 tourist representing 17.3% holds secondary school certificates; 6 tourist representing 8.0% holds primary school certificates; 10 tourist representing 13.3% hold other certificates/diploma certificates; 10 tourist representing 13.3% hold master degree; 36 tourist representing 48.0% hold bachelor degree. This implies that 36% of the tourists constitute of bachelor degree holders.

Original Article

Figure 2: Bar chart showing Educational Background of Tourists’ Analyses of Hypotheses

Table 3: Bivariate analysis of perceived attractiveness and destination image

		Perceived attractiveness	Destination image
Correlation Coefficient			
Sig. (2-tailed)		1.000	
Kendall's tau_b	Perceived attractiveness	.825**	.000
	Destination image	.825**	.000
N		75	75
Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.
N 75 **. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).			75

Table 3 above shows the bivariate analysis between perceived attractiveness and destination image. The result shows that perceived attractiveness has a positive significant relationship with destination image (.825**; .000). Thus, it is on this premise that the null hypothesis will be rejected and alternate hypothesis accepted.

Original Article

Table 4: Bivariate analysis of relaxation and responsiveness

		<u>Relaxation</u>	<u>Responsiveness</u>
	Correlation Coefficient		
	Relaxation		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	1.000	
	N	.	
	Correlation Coefficient	.75	.786**
Kendall's tau_b	Responsiveness	.786**	.000 75 1.000
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
	N	75	75

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 4 above shows the bivariate analysis between relaxation and responsiveness. The result indicates that relaxation has a positive significant relationship with responsiveness (.786**; .000). Based on this result, the null hypothesis is hereby rejected and alternate hypothesis accepted.

Discussion of findings

Based on the hypotheses results above, this study found that travel motivation has a positive significant relationship with tourist satisfaction in Port Harcourt Pleasure Park. These findings correspond with Thiumsak and Ruangkanjanases (2016) findings which indicates that perceived attractiveness on accommodation, shopping, restaurant & food, and attitude of Thai people, relaxation & recreation, and the overall destination image constitute travel motivating factors. Secondly, the findings of this study is also in line with Nor, Shareena, Siti and Syahmi (2016) results which revealed that destination image, tourist expectations, costs and risks and social-security have positive and significant influence on tourist satisfaction.

Conclusion

This study concludes that travel motivation that is measured on perceived attractiveness and relaxation has the capacity of fulfilling tourist satisfaction. This also implies that as tourists travel to destinations as a result of its attractiveness and relaxation purposes, responsiveness from the service providers and image of the destination enhances their satisfaction.

References

Baker, D.A. & Crompton, J.L. (2000). Quality, satisfaction and behavioral intentions. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 27(3), 785-804.

Bashar & Al-Ajlani, A.A. (2012). Motivating foreign tourists to visit the rural site in Jordan, village of Petra. *Australian Journal of Business and Management Research*, 2(5), 0107.

Beerli, A. & Martín, J.D. (2004). Tourists’ characteristics and the perceived image of tourist destinations: a quantitative analysis - A case study of Lanzarote, Spain. *Tourism Management*. 25(5), 623-636.

Original Article

- Bowie, D. & Chang, C. (2005). Tourist satisfaction: A view from a mixed international packaged tour,” *Journal of Vacation Marketing*, 11(4), 303-322.
- Chang, J. C. (2007). Travel motivations of package tour travelers. *Original Scientific Paper*, 55 (2), 157-176.
- Chi, C.G.Q. & Qu, H. (2008). Examining the structural relationships of destination image, tourist satisfaction and destination loyalty: An integrated approach. *Tourism Management*, 29, 624-636.
- Crompton, J.L. (1977). Motives for pleasure vacation. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 1 (4), 408-424.
- Crompton, J.L. (1979). An assessment of the image of Mexico as a vacation destination and the influence of geographical location upon that image. *Journal of Travel Research*, 17(4), 18-23.
- Fodness, D. (1994). Measuring tourist motivation. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 21, 55 –581.
- Hsi-Ying, H. (2016). The influence of travel motivation and destination image on destination choices of backpackers in Tainan. *Proceedings of the Eighth Asia-Pacific Conference on Global Business, Economics, Finance and Banking (AP16Singapore Conference), 21-23, July 2016, Singapore, 1-8.*
- Hsu, C.H.C. & Huang, S. (2008). *Travel motivation: a critical review of the concept’s development*. In A.G. Woodside and D. Martin (eds), *Tourism Management: Analysis, Behavior, and Strategy*, Cambridge: CAB International. <https://phpleasurepark.com/ppk2/other-facilities/>
- Hu, Y. & Ritchie, J. (1993). Measuring destination attractiveness: A contextual approach. *Journal of Travel Research*, 32, 25-34.
- Igi-global.com (2019). *What is tourist satisfaction?* Retrieved from <https://www.igi-global.com/dictionary/a-new-frontier-in-the-satisfaction-of-the-cultural-tourist/39285>
- Kandampully, J. & Hu, H.H. (2007). Do hoteliers need to manage image to retain loyal customers? *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 19(6), 435 – 443.
- Kotler, P. & Keller, K.L. (2009). *Marketing management*. (13th edn.). New Jersey: Pearson Education Inc, Upper Saddle River.
- Le, N. (2010). *Customers are said to be satisfied only if there are positive confirmations of expectation*. Master of Science in Management, Economics and Industrial Engineering, Politecnico Di Milano.
- March, R.G. & Woodside, A.G. (2005). *Tourism Behavior: Travelers’ decisions and actions*. CABI Publishing, Cambridge.
- Mullins, L.J. (2011). *Management & Organisational Behaviour*. (9th edn.). England: Pearson Education Limited.

Original Article

- Ninemeier, J.D. & Perdue, J. (2008). *Discovering hospitality and tourism: The World's Greatest Industry*. (2nd edn.). New Jersey: Pearson Prentice Hall.
- Nor, K.A., Shareena, M.H., Siti, D.M.W. & Syahmi, H. (2016). Tourists' satisfaction with a destination: An investigation on visitors to Langkawi Island. *British Journal of Marketing Studies*, 4(5), 1-20.
- Oom do Valle, P., Silva, J.A., Mendes, J. & Guerreiro, M. (2006). Tourist satisfaction and destination loyalty intention: A structural and categorical analysis. *Int. Journal of Business Science and Applied Management*, 1(1), 25-44.
- Schiffman, L.G. & Kanuk, L.L. (2004). *Consumer Behavior*. (8th edn.). NJ: Pearson Education, Inc.
- Severt, D., Wong, Y., Chen, P. & Breiter, D. (2007) Examining the motivation, perceived performance and behavioral intentions of convention attendees: Evidence from a regional conference. *Tourism Management*, 28, 399-408.
- Sharma, R. (2017). Tourist satisfaction with reference to accommodation. *International Journal of Scientific Research*, 6(12), 411-415.
- Sinding, K. & Waldstrom, C. (2014). *Organisational behaviour*. (5th edn.). UK: McGraw- Hill Education.
- Solnet, D. (2011). *Tourism & service management*. Contemporary Tourism Reviews. Oxford: Goodfellow Publishers Limited.
- Suanmali, S. (2014). Factors affecting tourist satisfaction: An empirical study in the Northern Part of Thailand. *SHS Web of Conferences* 12, 0102, 1-19.
- Tang, W.W. (2007). Impact of corporate image and corporate reputation on customer loyalty: A review. *Management Science and Engineering*, 1(2), 57 – 62.
- Thiumsak, T. & Ruangkanjanases, A. (2016). Factors Influencing International Visitors to Revisit Bangkok, Thailand. *Journal of Economics, Business and Management*, 4(3),220-230.
- Um, S., Chon, K. & Ro, H.Y. (2006). Antecedents of revisit intention. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 33(4), 1141-1158.
- Vanacore, A. & Erto, P. (2002). A probabilistic approach to measure hotel service quality. *Total Qual. Manag.*,13(2), 165-174.
- Vuuren, T., Lombard, M. & Tonder, E. (2012). Customer satisfaction, trust and commitment as predictors of customer loyalty within an optometric practice environment. *Southern African Business Review*, 16(3), 81 – 96.
- Zhang, Q.H., & Lam, T. (1999). An analysis of mainland Chinese visitors' motivations to visit Hong Kong. *Tourism Management*, 20, 587-594.